

Who should pay for Indological Research? The debate between 1884 and 1914

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Abstract: The Government of India, from 1870 onwards, paid for Indological research by funding its Archaeological Survey of India (ASI). Lord Ripon's Viceroyship (1880-84) created new funding streams, such as a 'Curatorship of Ancient Monuments', and an 'Epigraphical Survey'. Under the following, Viceroy budgets had to be cut. The Departments of Ancient Monuments and Epigraphy were jettisoned as soon as existing employment contracts ran out. Lord Dufferin then examined further cuts. It was proposed to dispense with the ASI's Director General. It was proposed to close two of the provincial ASI offices. It was proposed to abolish the ASI altogether. Lord Lansdowne (Viceroy from 1888 to 1894), who became Viceroy late in 1888, chose to abolish the ASI. He ordered all its operations to cease from October 1895. During the 1890s, three different answers to the titular question were vigorously debated. Thereafter, the Government of India settled on a funding mechanism that has served India for

* Professor Andrew Huxley died peacefully with his family at his side in the early hours of 29 November 2014. In one of our last exchanges, Andrew sent me a final draft of this paper and asked me to see it to publication. The article was complete but needed substantial editorial attention. I am very grateful to Dr. Jason Hawkes for shouldering the arduous task of chasing down the relevant bibliographic material and preparing the manuscript according to the *BIS* style. He devoted many hours to the text with a degree careful dedication that is exceptional. Thanks are also due to Gerd J.R. Mevissen for his friendship and support as editor of *BIS*. The editorial work was undertaken as part of *Politics, Ritual and Religion*, a project at the British Museum supported by the Leverhulme Trust. Many thanks are due to the Trust for their ongoing support. The subject of Prof. Huxley's article and his interpretation of events are no doubt controversial. They are, however, significant and well suited to our research project at the Museum. Our hope is that the importance of the issues raised by Prof. Huxley will be recognized and that this will prompt a much-needed scientific debate about the history and findings of this key phase of Indian archaeology and Indology.

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more than a century. I examine the correspondence between the debate's four institutional participants, *viz.* the Viceroy-in-Council, the Calcutta Departmental Secretary in charge of matters Indological, the India Office, and the Council of the Royal Asiatic Society. What started as a reasoned debate on funding turned, halfway through the 1890s, into something more conspiratorial.

Introduction

Until 1871 the Government of India funded Indological research through *ad hoc* temporary measures. After 1871, it took on the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI) as a permanent funding commitment. The staff's salaries were taken care of, but funding for serious excavations and for restoration of tumbling ruins remained *ad hoc*. Two of the ASI's first three Director Generals were long-lasting, and defined their eras: we speak of a 'Cunningham era' from 1871 to 1885, and of a 'Marshall era' from 1902 to 1928. Let us refer to the middle period of ASI history (1885-1901) as 'the interregnum'. This three-fold periodization – Cunningham, interregnum, and Marshall – resembles the process of change in the governance of the Royal Asiatic Society (RAS). From 1868 to 1887, T.E. Colebrook and William Vaux attempted to reform the *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* to meet the challenge of new Journals (such as *Academy*, *Athenaeum* and *Nineteenth Century*), which paid their contributors. From 1887 to 1905, Rhys Davids, a brilliant publicist, edited the *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*. From 1906 to 1917, John Fleet took over as Honorary Secretary and editor of the *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*. The bulk of the funding debate occurred in the 1890s during the ASI's interregnum, while Rhys Davids edited the *JRAS*.

The debate was between the *status quo* and its three rivals: the Viceroys Lansdowne, Elgin and Curzon. Viceroy Lansdowne endorsed the 'privatization model' between 1892 and 1894. Then Viceroy Elgin preferred the 'foreign donation model'. Viceroy Curzon worked to construct his idiosyncratic 'state patronage model' from December 1899. In 1904, while Curzon was on leave in London, the RAS ground to a halt over how Curzon's policy should be implemented. State patronage, as he had originally understood it, ceased to be government policy in December 1904. Yet it had an afterlife, which in 1906 led to further friction between the RAS and the India Office, as did the foreign donation model. Despite Curzon's angry opposition, a site

in the Buddhist Holy Land was excavated in 1904 with funds solicited from the European general public. The funding of this dig remained controversial until 1914.

In the next section I explain how Cunningham's contemporaries viewed his achievements at the ASI as his era drew to a close. I do so through the critical voices of four younger Indologists, all of whom wrote survey-of-the-field articles between 1887 and 1901 – Vincent SMITH (1889), James BURGESS (1893a), Georg BÜHLER (1895b), and John FLEET (1901).

Cunningham's final decade in India: 1875-85

Major Alexander Cunningham dominated archaeology in India throughout the 1860s and 1870s. This was partly because he was funded by the central government, rather than by those of the provinces. It was also because Cunningham was well connected to the Viceroy, his council, and their under-secretaries in Calcutta, as well as to literary circles. His father was a poet, his eldest brother the author of a controversial history of the Sikhs. Another brother produced editions of the Jacobean dramatists, whilst a third was a well-known antiquarian. Cunningham spent his hot seasons writing up his Reports and organizing his coin collection. He spent his cold seasons conducting survey tours of northern India. The survey tour was a systematic campaign of description, transcription, and listing, supplemented by occasional excavations. Because the "survey tourists" rarely spent more than three nights in one place, they had little opportunity for significant discovery. Excavation, if it took place at all, was a hit-and-run affair. Cunningham's priority when digging was to retrieve relic deposits from *stupas* by digging through the brickwork from top centre down to ground level. Three days was enough to dig through the brickwork, but not to replace the bricks and make good with mortar. Come the next monsoon, the hole in the *stupa* became a pond, which could only drain itself by collapsing the rest of the *stupa*. Cunningham did permanent damage to the main *stupas* at the two important Buddhist sites of Sanchi and Kasia. On his first visit to Kasia in 1861, "he drove a horizontal gallery into the centre of the building at its base without making any discovery" (CUNNINGHAM 1871: 77-78). Since then, reported Archibald CARLLEYLE (1883: 87), Cunningham's first assistant, the "stupa has been very much encroached upon and diminished in size". To make matters worse, CUNNINGHAM (1871:

78) confessed, “I did not expect to find anything”. James BURGESS (1893a: 44) deplored Cunningham’s belief that “the monument itself” is less valuable than “any buried relic casket” within. The better practice for the ASI, BURGESS said, should be to delineate “the site and present condition of any ruin before commencing an excavation”, and to demolish “nothing that by trouble could be preserved” *in situ* (*ibid.*).

Cunningham’s initial proposal for an Archaeological Survey had asked for a general survey of each site, along with ground plans of the important buildings. Also desirable were “photographic views of architecture and sculpture and careful facsimiles of all inscriptions” (SINGH 2004: 57-58). Looking back over his 19 years in office, did Cunningham make good on his proposals? As to his surveys and plans, the reports of the ASI contain only one architectural representation (of the temple at Sidnath) and this “so unlike the original, I defy any one to recognise it” (FERGUSON 1884: 76). His assistant, Joseph Beglar, was even worse. His “few attempts at drawing architectural details resemble the production of a half-educated schoolboy” (*ibid.*: 77). James FERGUSON, whose words these are, was notorious for his unparliamentary language. Vincent SMITH (1889: 188) used gentler words to make the same point, “No good purpose would now be served by dwelling on the obvious faults of his” reports. Cunningham’s ASI never acquired a photographer, so produced no photos of sites and artefacts. His epigraphic achievements are contested. On the one hand, he published several important Buddhist inscriptions for the first time. On the other hand, his knowledge of early Prakrit, the language of most of these inscriptions, was inadequate: “His philological theories were to the last those of an amateur” (COTTON 1893: 513). Cunningham’s successor, BURGESS (1893a: 44), set out the principles of best practice in this field,

“Obtain the best possible mechanical reproductions of inscriptions, never trusting to the most perfect eye-copies ... I have always tried to lay such facsimiles before scholars whose reputation was a guarantee for the accuracy of their translations and the value of their comments.”

SMITH (1889: 170), who spent two years indexing all 23 volumes of Cunningham’s reports, complained that “the technical labours of the archaeologist are not yet sufficiently advanced to enable the historian to take his place”. Cunningham’s epigraphic work, in other words, provides an insufficient basis for diachronic analysis.

Identifying the sites of the Buddhist Holy Land was the ASI's central task. Cunningham's first funding application in 1848 was to identify the sites mentioned by the Chinese pilgrims, Faxian and Xuanzang. His second, in 1861, sought an "archaeological investigation of upper India which would follow the tracks of Xuanzang" (SINGH 2004: 58). Cunningham did as promised. His survey tours concentrated on those parts of northern India (the Punjab, and the North-Western Provinces and Oudh) where the pilgrims went, to the exclusion of Orissa and Bengal, which were rich in Hindu sites. Not only did Cunningham privilege Buddhism over Hinduism, he privileged mediaeval Buddhist geography over ancient Buddhist geography. The Chinese pilgrims visited India eight to ten centuries after the Buddha died. Their travel guides describe the Buddhist pilgrim sites then in vogue. One of Buddhism's best known texts, the *Sutta of the Great Decease* (Pali *Mahāparinibbāna Sutta*), describes a much earlier geography in which only four pilgrimage sites really matter: the location of the Buddha's birth (Lumbini), of his enlightenment (Uruvela), of his first sermon (Isipatana), and of his death (Kusinagara). To these four sites, the Buddha prophesied, "believers, brethren and sisters of the Order, or devout men and devout women" will come.¹ Where are they? Francis Buchanan (1762-1829) was the first European to identify Uruvela with the ruins of Bodhgaya in Bihar [24°41'N, 84°59'E]. He picked up the information during his stay at the Burmese court. James Prinsep (1799-1840) first identified Isipatana with the ruins at Sarnath, a few miles northeast of Varanasi [25°23'N, 83°02'E]. Cunningham's most urgent task was to locate the Buddha's birthplace and death-place. In 1861, he visited Kasia [26°50'N, 83°53'E] 25 miles east of Gorakhpur, and identified it as Kusinagara. In 1875, after toying with another site, Cunningham endorsed Lumbini as lying near Bhuila [26°50'N, 82°42'E] between the Rapti and the Gogra Rivers. FERGUSSON (1884: 77) doubted Cunningham, writing that "He has contributed almost literally nothing to our knowledge of archaeology or architectural geography". John FLEET (1901: 26), writing 16 years later, agreed that some of Cunningham's "most confidently asserted identifications of the sites mentioned by *Xuanzang* are unquestionably wrong". As to the Buddha's birthplace being at Bhuila, FERGUSSON (1884: 77) was unconvinced,

1 *Dīgha Nikāya* ii 141 (see RHYS DAVIDS 2002: 154).

“It may be at Bhuila, as General Cunningham thinks, but the evidence ... will not stand a moment’s investigation. My own impression is that it was considerably more to the southward.”

Vincent SMITH decided in 1896 that the Buddha’s death-place could not possibly be at Kasia (see SMITH 1896). Over the next 15 years, he wrote several articles arguing that Kusinagara would be found in the northwestern corner of Bihar. John Marshall’s ASI, in order to confute Smith’s campaign, was later forced to spend valuable resources re-digging Kasia and Savatthi.

Most of those interested in the funding of Indology felt that Cunningham’s last decade running the ASI had been a flop. These critics felt even more animus against Cunningham’s Survey Assistants, Archibald Carlleyle and Joseph Beglar,

“General Cunningham chooses his assistants ... because of their incompetence, in order that they may not forestall the credit ... from the great work he one day hopes to be able to publish on Indian archaeology” (FERGUSSON 1884: 77).

In similar vein, F.S. GROWSE wrote in 1887, “The unrevised lucubrations of General Cunningham’s assistants are a tissue of trivial narrative and the crudest theories”.² Behind these criticisms was the controversial question of restoration. While Cunningham left his ruins worse than he found them, at two important Buddhist sites the Assistants improved the ruins, so the sites could be reborn as functioning Buddhist pilgrimage sites. At Kasia, Carlleyle created a virtual Kusinagara, a place where pilgrims could worship a statue of the recumbent Buddha smiling as he slips through the end of his life. At Bodhgaya, Beglar repurposed the main *stupa* (the Mahabodhi) and its environs at huge expense to become a formal garden of trees and ruins surrounding the magnificently restored main *stupa*. He foresaw a great demand,

“This Temple is one of the places which travellers from Europe are almost certain to visit, to say nothing of Burmese, Japanese, Ceylonese, Nepalese, Tibetans and Siamese. Chinese pilgrims have not yet come, but probably will” (BEGLAR 1898).

² For GROWSE’s written evidence to the Public Service Commission (1887), see BURGESS 1905: 141.

He further recommended building an infrastructure to meet the demand. A bungalow should be constructed “for the accommodation of European travellers, lady visitors, and of the more distinguished foreign Asiatic visitors” (*ibid.*). The last five words suggest that Bodhgaya might become a place for diplomacy – a place where Buddhist statesmen can exchange views having worshipped together at the most sacred site in the Buddhist world. The most virulent critic of the Kasia and Bodhgaya restorations, James FERGUSSON (1884), attacked these plans on aesthetic grounds. Vincent SMITH, another critic, implied that the Assistants had restored the wrong buildings. At Bodhgaya, which “was ‘restored’ almost beyond recognition by Mr. Beglar” (SMITH 1889: 183), we see not the original Ashokan building built in the 2nd century BCE, but a Burmese recreation built late in the 13th century CE. At Kasia, SMITH implies that Carlleyle restored the wrong ruin: the real Kusinagara is to be found a hundred miles to the north-east (*ibid.*).

The 1880 British election was one of the very few to be influenced by events in India. Gladstone’s attack on Viceroy Lytton’s unpopular war in Afghanistan led to Lord Ripon replacing Lytton with a mandate to make peace in Kabul and avoid war on Mandalay. As a Liberal, Ripon was in favour of increased funding for education and research. Though he funded three new posts, it would seem that he did not trust Cunningham to spend the money wisely: the new posts were not part of the ASI. At the new Department of Ancient Monuments, Major Henry Cole was appointed Curator in 1881, and Major J.B. Keith his full-time Assistant in 1882. The Department of Ancient Monuments was intended to be a central clearing-house through which all provincial restoration projects could be reviewed. There was talk of setting up a ‘committee of taste’ to assist the department, but wiser counsels prevailed. Ripon’s third new post was the Government Epigrapher, to which John Fleet was appointed in 1882, earning the same salary (Rs.1400 per month) that he got as a middle-ranking member of the Bombay Civil Service (HARTINGTON 1882). Ripon gave Fleet a three-year contract.

These appointments are best understood as Ripon’s mediation between the two schools, Classical and Modernist, which contested the Indological field. The classicists were descended from Renaissance humanists like Erasmus and Scaliger. They were dedicated to texts, to preparing proper editions, and to compiling the necessary dictionaries and concordances. Early in the

19th century, Bopp and Schlegel had extended Classicism to include the study of Sanskrit. By 1881, Germany supported 34 Orientalist Professors, whilst in England the sparse band of classicists were led by Max Müller of Oxford. The modernists preferred a three-dimensional artefact to a text. They aimed to take photographs, to draw up plans, and to make accurate replicas for distribution. The modernists started with industrial capitalism: add art to the factory floor, and value will be added to the factory's products. They valued non-European art equally with European. From Asia came strange new forms of beauty that might, when applied to a Staffordshire tea-set or to a showpiece building site, improve the pottery company's profits and the architect's reputation. Sir Henry Cole (1808-82) was London's most influential Modernist. His son, Henry Cole, brought his father's aims and techniques to India. J.B. Keith, his assistant, was an enthusiastic Modernist. However John Fleet, the epigraphist, was *ex officio* a Classicist. Ripon gave his patronage to both schools, but he gave the modernists twice as many jobs as the classicists.

The elder Henry Cole won the patronage of Prince Albert, and helped organize the Great Exhibition of 1851. He persuaded the Government to spend the profits of the Exhibition by building *Albertopolis* in South Kensington. Cole's South Kensington Museum was to provide designers with photographs and replicas of Chinese, Indian, and Islamic art. The younger Henry Cole (born in 1843) worked for the North-Western Provinces and Oudh Public Works Department. He was tasked, in 1868, with surveying the archaeological sites of the North-Western Provinces and Oudh and its neighbours.³ His father lobbied for a team from India to spend a year in London learning the techniques of replica making. Young Henry led two corporals and a sergeant of the Royal Engineers. The team worked at the South Kensington Museum in 1869 and 1870. They returned carrying 28 tonnes of replica-making equipment and consumables. At the eastern gateway of Sanchi they tested their skills. They made 112 elastic gelatine moulds and sent them back to South Kensington for casting. The casts were displayed in Paris, Edinburgh and Dublin to huge acclaim. A sub-committee of the British Department of Education in London (controlled by the elder Henry) funded the team to take moulds at Fatehpur Sikri; but by 1871 funding from all sources had dried up.

3 This led to the publication of two books; see COLE 1873 and 1889.

Thereafter, though nominally still at the Public Works Department, young Henry was permitted to spend a year or two in London cataloguing the Indian collection in his father's museum (see COLE 1874). A few years later under Viceroy Lytton, he held a roving commission to inspect monuments across India as an Officer on Special Duty. Lytton applied to regularize the post under the title Curator of Ancient Monuments. By the time London approved, Viceroy Ripon was in office.

At the Department of Ancient Monuments, young Henry Cole regarded the job not just as providing an all-Indian clearing-house for techniques and information, but also as supervising all replica and restoration projects in India. Since such projects were funded from Provincial budgets, friction between Cole and the Provincial Governors was inevitable. The first battle was over the wonderful carved panels at the Amaravati *stupa*. Should they be preserved *in situ*, as Cole demanded, or moved to a museum, as the Madras Government preferred? James Burgess, now the Archaeological Surveyor of Southern India, agreed with Madras. The resulting slanging match between Burgess and Cole lasted three years, and was resolved in Burgess' favour (SINGH 2004: 210). Its lasting result was to place Burgess (who had been trained as an architect, and thus might have had modernist tendencies) firmly on the side of the classicists.

Burgess' second battle was over Beglar's restoration of Bodhgaya, the most expensive project then under way in India. In 1882, the month before Ashley Eden left, Cole inspected Beglar's work and endorsed his plans. While Eden still governed Bengal, Cole avoided any quarrel. Three months later, Cole began firing off memos to Calcutta criticizing the Bodhgaya project.⁴ In August 1883, Governor Thompson's Council complained to the Viceroy that Cole was "constantly interfering with and criticising" Beglar's plan (SINGH 2004: 210). The funding for Ancient Monuments ended in January 1884, and Cole's Department closed for good. John Fleet created no such difficulties. He got on quietly with the Gupta inscriptions, and published his brilliant edition as volume three of the *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum* (FLEET 1888). Vincent SMITH (1889: 169) hailed it as "of almost equal importance" to James Prinsep's work on the Ashokan inscriptions. Fleet's funding

4 Cole recognized that Beglar was "simply following instructions" (SINGH 2004: 228) in relation to Bodhgaya. Presumably, Ashley Eden was the *eminence gris*.

ran out in December 1885, and he returned to his normal duties as Collector at Sholapur. In a sense, the Epigraphical Survey survived. The India Office agreed to fund a young German Indological graduate, Eugen Hultzsch, to work on the Dravidian inscriptions (BURGESS 1905: 146). German Indologists were cheaper to employ than middle ranking Indian Colonial Service men.

In 1882, Ripon appointed Edward Buck as Calcutta's Secretary of Revenue and Agriculture. Buck shared the Modernist agenda. Now that he had the Viceroy's ear, he might get it implemented. In 1885, Buck convened the Committee for the Promotion of Industrial Art in India, whose aim was to develop an export market in Indian craft goods:

“The carved steering chair of an Irrawaddy boat cannot be rigged up on the poop of a Thames steamer. The anklets and nose-rings of an Indian beauty cannot be worn by a lady of fashion in Europe. To what extent then can Eastern designs and workmanship be applied to Western forms?” (BUCK 1883: 1-2).

Buck planned to build museums in each of “the great Indian centres” to act as “sample rooms where the best examples of Indian craftsmanship might be seen” (*ibid.*). With the assistance of Major Hendley of Jaipur and John Lockwood Kipling of Lahore, he started the *Journal of Indian Art and Industry*, a glossy monthly dedicated to the modernist agenda. Lord Ripon's council gave assurances that Buck's ambitious plans would be funded. When Dufferin replaced Ripon, these assurances proved worthless and the money was diverted into new posts for the classical archaeologists. The modernists whom Ripon had employed (Cole and his assistant J.B. Keith), and those to whom Ripon had promised funding (Buck, Lockwood Kipling, and Hendley), licked their wounds and planned their comeback.

Viscount Dufferin instigated a war in Burma that cost more than anticipated. Cuts had to be made. He cut the budgets for both the modernist arts and crafts project and the restoration of ancient sites. The Tory Viceroy also planned cuts to the ASI budget, but Director-General Cunningham sacrificed himself in return for the continued funding of his assistants. Cunningham's salary was split between Joseph Beglar, who became Surveyor of the Bengal Circle, and H.B.W. Garrick, in charge of the Punjab Circle. Meanwhile Alfred Lyall, the Governor of the North-Western Provinces and Oudh, hired new staff to create a North-Western Provinces and Oudh Circle. Early in 1885 he put

J.B. Keith in charge, with Purna Chundar Mukherji as assistant.⁵ Towards the end of the year he added Alois Führer, the Curator of the Lucknow Provincial Museum, to the roster. The ASI now had five men working in North India, and three men working independently in Western and Southern India. James Burgess ran Bombay and Madras as his personal fiefdom. A note to file in 1873 states that Burgess “would not work willingly under” Cunningham, because he “is a disciple of Mr Fergusson”.⁶ But Dufferin insisted that someone be in overall control of the ASI. Burgess, the obvious candidate, was reluctant. It took a year, and an increased pay offer, to secure Burgess as Director-General for the whole of India.

Once installed, Burgess declared war on the recent appointees in North India. These recruits lacked, for the most part, “the necessary qualifications and were unnecessarily expensive” (BURGESS 1893a: 43). He was particularly hostile to modernists like Keith, to native archaeologists like Mukherji, and to those associated with expensive restoration projects like Beglar. Governor Thompson of Bengal managed to protect Beglar’s job. Governor Lyall of NWPO fought hard for Mukherji’s job, but lost. Burgess insisted that Mukherji be replaced by an English architectural draftsman fresh off the boat. Keith was eased out of his job in circumstances so murky that Edward Buck assured him of financial compensation,

“Unhappily there were those who took no interest in conservation and desired to secure my appointment for a German, Doctor Führer ... And I was the victim” (KEITH 1900).

This letter of KEITH’s describes the state of the battle between the modernists and classicists at the end of the 1890s,

“For years the necessities of Indian Archaeology have fallen into the hands of philologists, who have made it a preserve in pressing home the exploded theories of Professor Max Müller” (*ibid.*).

Burgess made too many enemies to survive as Director-General. For the brief time he held the post, he was often thwarted by officials. BURGESS (1893a: 47) quoted approvingly an article by J. GIBBS (1886: 562),

5 Due to sickness, Keith did not take up his office until 1886.

6 Note for record, 8 August 1873, cited in SINGH 2004: 191.

“It is surprising how little support or encouragement archaeology meets with from the great majority of officers of government ... Those who thought the whole subject purely dilettantism and unpractical, ... used all the powers of the Secretariat to delay and thwart the work.”

Burgess retired from India in 1889, officially due to injuries sustained in an elephant accident. He was happy to reveal the real reason: the 1885 hirings in the ASI were “confessedly expensive and expense in a small Department is a mortal sin in the eyes of Government. I am retiring to effect a saving” (BURGESS 1893a: 45).

The Privatization Model, 1888-95

Looking back on the Ripon and Dufferin years, a correspondent in the *Pioneer* complained that the Government employed,

“at very high salaries learned antiquarians and a large and most expensive staff of officers to pervade the past and patrol the night of time in a vague and general way - and with vague and general results” (ANONYMOUS 1891).

Lord Lansdowne, who became Viceroy late in 1888, agreed that “the scale of expenditure is larger than is necessary or desirable” (cf. SINGH 2004: 197). He set up a finance committee to cut government expenditure, with particular reference to the ASI (*ibid.*). They concluded “that archaeological investigations should not be altogether abandoned but should be reduced to the permanent minimum at which it is desirable to maintain it”.⁷ Burgess was pressured to leave in 1889. The Punjab and Bengal Circles were closed down in 1890. That left the ASI with five European staff.⁸ In 1891, the funding burden was shifted from Calcutta to the Provinces. In 1892 the remaining five archaeologists were sent notices of dismissal: the ASI would close completely as from 1 October 1895.

From 1889 to 1891, Lansdowne’s policy was to trim jobs but keep the department. From 1892 to 1894, his policy was that no more public money be spent on archaeology and epigraphy. He was responding to a long running

7 Order of 5 May 1890, cited by Nayanjot LAHIRI 1997: 129.

8 Cousins, Rae and Hultzsch in South and West India; Führer and Edmond Smith in the NWPO Circle.

debate over who, if not the Government, should pay for Indological research. Two sources of donor were discussed in the 1880s – rich Englishmen and native princes. James BURGESS (1893a: 47) was pessimistic about Englishmen because their interest in India “is not yet sufficiently developed. Instead, may we not expect this work to be wisely and munificently furthered by [India’s] own native princes and educated Hindus?”. Vincent SMITH made his appeal to an English audience through the *Quarterly Review*. Calcutta, he conceded, “is entitled to ask for the aid of private enterprise” (SMITH 1889: 185), but,

“Is it too much to hope that some individual of the moderate funds needed will emulate the example of Lord Elgin and enrich the national collection with the [Amaravati] marbles?” (*ibid.*: 185).

To Europeans, he conceded, “Indian subjects are notoriously repulsive” (*ibid.*: 187); they preferred reading news of excavations in Palestine and Egypt. The classicists were coming to realize that higher funding for Indian digs would depend on making Indology more popular. Burgess and Smith (both of whom were classicists) envisaged partial privatization, with gifts supplementing state funding. Full privatization (no state funding whatever) was a modernist policy, one already recognized as likely,

“Government may get tired of paying £21,240 a year to put an end to the work of the Archaeological Survey in the North-West Provinces. At present all concerned are anxious. In some provinces the work has been cut short, and there is no knowing what a Government, intent on sanitation, may not give up” (AN ENGLISH VISITOR 1891).

The modernist who pushed hardest for full privatization was Edward Buck, apparently in revenge for Lord Dufferin’s destruction of the Modernist project in India. Georg BÜHLER (1895a) equated the policy with the person in a private letter to Rhys Davids,

“Now is the time for friends of true scholarship and scholarly research to bestir themselves. If Sir E. Buck’s plan is carried through, we shall have another period of perfectly useless dilettante work.”

Buck was not an evil bureaucrat. Indeed, he was “the despair of bullet-headed, metallic-souled bureaucrats of the type so well-known in India” (H.E.M.J. 1916). Nor was he hostile to India and its past. “Nothing pleased him more than to plunge with a native hunter into a Himalayan forest, which

he would penetrate before the dawn of day” (*ibid.*). But Buck admired a past more recent than the long-time-gone of the classicists. He admired the tradition built up by generations of Hindu metal workers of Lucknow and of Muslim artists of Lahore, and hoped to ease their passage into the global marketplace. Modernism aimed to make Indian craftsmen more prosperous, which appealed to a Liberal agenda. Buck’s Liberal politics aimed to please the native population. The classicists’ faraway past was inhabited by Buddhists and Jains, who carried very little weight in the developing political agenda of 1880s India.

Back in Europe, modernists and classicists fought a bitter war over control of the Congresses of Orientalists. The Congresses had been founded in 1873 to bring European scholars together to share knowledge “*de omnibus rebus orientalibus antiquis aut modernis*” (CUST 1897: 89). During the early years of Lansdowne’s Viceroyship, the organization split. Max Müller’s 1892 Congress brought a group of classicists together who would go on to play a leading role in the funding debates: Lord Reay (soon to become the Royal Asiatic Society’s President), Rhys Davids (the Society’s Secretary and Editor), Professor Georg Bühler (of Vienna), and Vincent Smith (of the North-Western Provinces and Oudh). Lord Reay, a Dutchman of Scottish descent, served the Dutch Empire until his mid-thirties. In Dutch politics, he was a Leftist: in British politics, a Liberal. He was Governor of Bombay (1885-90), and supported James Burgess against his critics in Bengal and the North-Western Provinces and Oudh. He would soon become junior minister at the India Office in the Liberal imperialist government of 1894-95. Rhys Davids, an Essex man of Welsh descent, served the British Empire in Ceylon until his early thirties. He was a lifelong Liberal. After scandal forced his return to England, some Orientalist editors refused to print his contributions. Max Müller, however, offered him translation work, and supported Rhys Davids’ career thereafter. The RAS hired Rhys Davids in 1887 for his skills as an editor and a publicist. For the first five years he was peripheral to RAS decision-making. It was the schism between the London Congresses of 1891 and 1892 that brought Rhys Davids into the inner circle. Georg Bühler, an Austrian professor of Hanoverian descent, served the British Empire in Bombay and Rajasthan. Max Müller helped him get a job with the Government of India. Bühler inspected schools and collected Sanskrit manuscripts between 1863 and 1880. After Burgess lost his Director-Generalship, Bühler supervised

Führer's digs in the North-Western Provinces and Oudh, and acted as adviser on early Indian inscriptions. Vincent Smith, a Dubliner from the intellectual wing of the Protestant ascendancy, decided in the late 1880s to devote his remaining energies to Indian history instead of his civil service career.

Vincent Smith had an ace up his sleeve – he knew of two, possibly three, “undiscovered” pillars just inside the Nepalese border in the foothills of the Palpa Pass. At the London conference of 1892 he may have mentioned these to Reay, Rhys Davids, and Bühler. In 1893, Führer and Burgess used rumours of their existence to raise awareness of the threat to ASI funding. FÜHRER described a single Ashokan pillar in Nepal covered in enough different inscriptions to keep the classicists busy for decades,

“The pillar is in a perfect state of preservation, and contains, besides the seven well-known pillar edicts of Asoka, two new edicts addressed to the Buddhist clergy of the country of the Visas ... This new version of the seven edicts, already known to us from six other pillars, is of great importance for the interpretation of these documents as they are engraved according to a different script” (AN ARCHAEOLOGICAL CORRESPONDENT 1893).⁹

No such pillar has ever surfaced, nor did Burgess ever explain its non-appearance. It is hard to resist the conclusion that Führer and Burgess were engaged in a publicity stunt.

The Foreign Donation Model, 1895-1914

Alois Führer soon learnt the futility of seeking donations from Indian aristocrats and from the British middle class. In 1888 he approached the Maharani of Balrampur for funds to dig at Savatthi, but was unsuccessful (ANONYMOUS 1888). In the summer of 1891, he took the unusual step of appealing to the British public to support further digging at Mathura. He did this by private letter to Vincent Smith (then the Deputy Commissioner at Muzaffarnagar), itemizing the various grants he had received over the last three years and explaining that “I might have done much more, if I had more money at my disposal” (SMITH 1891). He wondered whether “some antiquarian societies at home might be induced to contribute some small sums” towards the Rs.6000

9 That FÜHRER was the author of this article is shown by BURGESS 1893b.

over the next three years which would be enough “to do Mathura thoroughly” (*ibid.*). SMITH forwarded Führer’s letter to *The Academy*, adding,

“If, Sir, you are willing to undertake to receive contributions, I shall have much pleasure in opening the list with a subscription of £5” (*ibid.*).

Nothing more was heard of this appeal, which presumably fell flat. During the next three years, Führer crossed the line into criminality. In 1894 he announced that during his short tour of Burma he had discovered the three oldest inscriptions ever found in that country. This, remarked Louis FINOT (1922), was the beginning of “the all-too famous Dr Führer’s ... scandalous career of forgery which would, some years later, come to an end in Kapilavastu”. It marked also the zenith of Führer’s reputation in London. An anonymous overview article kept his name in the public mind nine months after the pillar stunt. He “is probably the only scientific excavator in India worthy to rank with Dr. Dörpfeld and Prof. Petrie. But he is prevented by public parsimony” (see COTTON 1894).

Führer had learned that in the bold new world of privatized Indian archaeology, the future lay in appealing to foreign governments and European professors. Gradually, the Viceroy-in-Council, the India Office, and the Royal Asiatic Society came to share Führer’s opinion. In June 1895, lobbying by Lord Elgin in Calcutta, and by Lord Reay in London, won a reprieve for the five remaining ASI staff. They were to continue to work on an annual basis pending consultations between Calcutta and the local governments. Robert Cust asked Bühler to formulate detailed proposals for “the continuation of the archaeological and epigraphic work in India” (see BÜHLER 1895b: 660). Bühler put forward a three point plan: to save the jobs of the ASI staff currently employed, to make use of European experts as consultants, and to do one important dig a year in each province.¹⁰ What the scholars of Europe need, he said, is “new authentic documents” from the pre-Ashoka period. They will “only be found underground” at a considerable depth (*ibid.*). The “expectation” that they will turn up is “by no means unfounded” (*ibid.*: 656). Three years of consultation with the provincial governments began in 1895. The skeleton staff was kept on under a succession of annual contracts. In 1898, Calcutta concluded that it could neither disband the Survey altogether, nor keep it in its present enfeebled state.

10 BÜHLER (1895b) mentions Taxila, Mathura and Patna as suitable sites.

Lord Reay became Under-Secretary of State for India in Lord Rosebery's Liberal imperialist administration. The new team at the India Office determined to lobby hard for the ASI. Two conduits were used. George Grierson led a campaign from the Indian Museum at Calcutta, while Georg Bühler canvassed opinion in the *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*. Bühler, Grierson, and Lord Reay, were present in Geneva for the Tenth Congress of Orientalists.¹¹ There they helped to build a European climate of opinion on Archaeology in India. The first locus of lobbying was the Trustees of the Indian Museum, who proposed that Government fund a conservation project aimed at the Ashokan inscriptions. It was not the most ambitious of projects: rather than protect them from "all the vicissitudes of an Indian climate" (GRIERSON 1895a), they would take casts of them for display in a new Ashoka gallery in the museum. Grierson travelled to Geneva to propose that the Congress urge the Government of India to protect the inscriptions themselves, as well as displaying the casts. Discussion of the proposal was led by Bühler, Senart and Burgess: "three of the great authorities on Indian epigraphy now living" (*ibid.*). In "important speeches" they urged the importance of conserving the Ashokan corpus of rock and pillar inscriptions (GRIERSON 1895b). In November, Bühler lent more weight to Grierson's campaign. Writing demi-officially to the Indian Museum, BÜHLER (1894) offered a list of sites to dig,

"The way to obtain what is wanted – inscriptions older than the 3rd century – is to dig deep [at] Patna, Kosambi ... Ojjayani, Ramnagar ... To excavate deep and thoroughly is the point."

Grierson passed the letter to the relevant under-secretary in Calcutta.

Bühler delivered his lecture on the past and future of Indian archaeology at the Royal Asiatic Society on 11 June, 1895. William SINCLAIR, an old Bombay hand with interests in the life sciences and human antiquities, made a barbed contribution to the discussion. While conceding that "in the present state of Indian finance, the Government of India cannot be expected to spend much money on research" (SINCLAIR 1895: 664), he preferred that such money as there was should be given to members of the Revenue, Educational or Public Works Departments, rather than to the ASI. The ordinary civil servants

11 Lord Reay spoke on behalf of Britain to thank the Geneva Organizing Committee for its welcoming address; cf. REAY 1895.

are now as well informed as the specialists of twenty years ago, and anyway the ASI archaeologists are not to be trusted,

“There are, indeed, competent scholars outside of the services; but their presence only requires acknowledgment here, as an archaeological officer of Government must necessarily be its servant, and under its full control” (*ibid.*).

Possibly SINCLAIR was referring to Führer’s very recent discovery of the Nigliva Ashokan pillar and inscription. More probably he was referring to the 1893 publicity stunt announcing the “discovery” in Nepal of a nine-edict pillar, written in a new script.

In July, Lord Rosebery’s administration lost power, and with it Lord Reay. His lobbying lost impetus for the next four months. In December he persuaded the governing council of the RAS to form a sub-committee to protest “the proposed abolition of the Archaeological Survey” (ROYAL ASIATIC SOCIETY 1895).¹² Six months later it came back with plans to launch an “India Exploration Fund” (ROYAL ASIATIC SOCIETY 1896).¹³ Their inspiration was the Egypt Exploration Fund, which had been founded in 1883 to raise private money for the excavation of Pharaonic antiquities. By charging members an annual subscription, the Egypt Exploration Fund raised over £2,000 a year, chiefly from Britain and America (ANONYMOUS 1894).¹⁴ Its membership was broad enough that new members in effect recruited themselves. It could print enough of its archaeological reports to achieve the required economies of scale.¹⁵ The Egypt Exploration Fund provided an attractive funding model for the Orientalists, but there would have been opposition voices: unlike India, Egypt was merely within the British sphere of interest. Egypt under the Khedive felt foreign enough to deserve charitable donations from the British, but India was the heart of the British Empire – to ask for charity was to suggest

12 Robert Sewell and Rhys Davids were both in attendance at this meeting of the Royal Asiatic Society council.

13 Lord Reay was to chair the organisation.

14 In 1891-92, £2,500 was raised; in 1893-94 over £2,100 ‘almost entirely due to annual subscriptions in England, America and the Colonies’.

15 The Council discussed whether to produce a popular *Report on Indian Archaeology* to drum up support, but held back. Probably the number of potential supporters was not large enough to cover printing costs.

that Government had under-funded archaeology in India. Besides, Egypt had a local organisation, Service des Antiquités en Egypte, to receive the donations. The council of the RAS saw the lack of a credible counter-party in India to receive the gifts as the stumbling block. It minuted to shelve these plans pending “the decision of the Indian Government as to their Archaeological Survey” (ROYAL ASIATIC SOCIETY 1896). This first iteration of the India Exploration Fund was shelved for 15 months.

Lord Reay’s fund-raising in London coincided with Führer’s discoveries in the Nepal Terai. The first news of the Nigliva Pillar and its Ashokan inscription reached Europe in mid-1895. Führer spun this as the “rediscovery” of the 1893 publicity stunt pillar, but it is hard to equate the five fragmentary lines found at Nigliva with the nine lengthy edicts of the 1893 pillar. The latter was the longest of all the Ashokan Pillar Inscriptions; the former was among the shortest. The latter was entirely consistent with the Ashokan corpus, the former something hitherto unseen. For over a year Führer kept quiet about Nigliva’s significance as a signpost to the Buddha’s birthplace and hometown. Then, two days before the London meeting, which first raised the notion of an Indian Exploration Fund, he splashed it. “The magnificent monuments” of ancient Kapilavatthu are “undoubtedly” to be found in the Taulehwa region, which includes Nigliva and Paderia (FÜHRER 1897). In December 1896, Führer announced the discovery of the Paderia pillar and inscription, and telegraphed to the world press that this marked Lumbini, the Buddha’s birthplace.

The Eleventh Oriental Congress was to be held in Paris from the 5th to the 12th September 1897. Its location was chosen to heal the schism of 1892-95. Here, Lord Reay chose to launch his plan for pan-European funding of Indian archaeology. Professor Senart of the University of Paris proposed a new sub-committee, La Commission chargée de la formation de l’Association Internationale pour l’exploration archéologique de l’Inde, to pursue the question of subsidizing archaeological exploration in India. Senart was to chair, with England represented by Lord Reay and Alfred Lyall, Austria-Hungary by Georg Bühler, Germany by Pischel, the Netherlands by M. Kern, Russia by Serge d’Oldenberg, Italy by Count Pullé. The Congress resolved to set up a sub-committee, the Indian Exploration Fund, based in London, to pursue the question of subsidizing archaeological exploration in India. RHYS-DAVID’S

correspondence with his wife gives more details. He was busy throughout Monday 6 September on what he called “the Kapilavastu question” (RHYS DAVIDS 1897). Bühler tried to set up a three-way breakfast meeting with Grierson and Rhys Davids, but Grierson had other breakfast plans, so the three convened a “special sub-committee” after the morning session to draft the resolution. At tea-time, Bühler and Rhys Davids met Reay for further discussion of the draft. Then, at 7 pm, Rhys Davids and Reay discussed it with Sir Alfred Lyall (*ibid.*). The question was delicate because,

“Even at this moment Dr. Führer carries out his investigations ... and it is scarcely an exaggeration to say that all Indianists have their attention fixed on the debris which will give us back this forgotten corner of the Nepalese Terai” (SENART 1898).

Once again Führer’s Terai discoveries drove the publicity for the Indian Exploration Fund.

After the Paris Congress, Lord Reay and Alfred Lyall spent nine months negotiating with the India Office and the Viceroy’s council. Reay and Lyall had taken the precaution of getting certain “eminent representatives of Indianism” to sign a letter in support. Meanwhile, on 6 January 1898, Senart submitted his main proposal for the second iteration of the Indian Exploration Fund. Senart tactfully marvelled at how successfully the English people and their Government had undertaken the civilisatory task that has fallen to them. However, the study of ancient India had recently undergone a vast expansion. The task of understanding India’s past being so immense, there was perhaps room for people outside England to expedite from time to time “a dig at this locality, or an exploration of that problem” (*ibid.*). Of course, he added, the ASI would have a veto. There was no point in the Indian Exploration Fund anticipating digs that the ASI would shortly carry out. SENART concluded that the Indian Exploration Fund’s role of channelling funds from Europe to India via London would be modest, compared to the government of India’s “infinitely predominant” role (*ibid.*).

Following Senart’s submission, events moved rapidly. In January 1898, Lord Reay told his Secretary to put the Indian Exploration Fund on the agenda for the next RAS Council meeting (REAY 1898a). The RAS resolved to put resources at the disposal of the Indian Exploration Fund “until the fund shall be established as a permanent institution” (ROYAL ASIATIC SOCIETY 1898a).

In February, BÜHLER told Reay's Secretary that he was "glad that the Council of the Society" had taken the action required by Sir A. Lyall, adding that it was "about time" (BÜHLER 1898). At the end of February, Reay was appointed as President of the Indian Exploration Fund; the RAS' Secretary, Rhys Davids, describing him as "notre excellent confrère" (REAY 1898b).¹⁶ On 14 July 1898, the Viceroy-in-Council informed Lord Hamilton, Secretary of State for India, of their approval of Senart's offer, subject to two stringent conditions: that Calcutta's consent was required before any dig could proceed, and that artefacts discovered during excavations could not be removed to Europe, except for such duplicate items as Calcutta might allow (ELGIN 1898). Senart agreed to the conditions, and convened the Committee that would bring the Indian Exploration Fund into existence. In December 1898, the India Office expressed its pleasure that Lord Reay had agreed to be President of the Indian Exploration Fund Central Committee (ROYAL ASIATIC SOCIETY 1898c). At this meeting the final stage of the funding channel was revealed. Donations received from Europe and from Britain should be held in an Indian Exploration Fund bank account in London under the supervision of the RAS. In celebration of the end of a protracted process of negotiation, the English members of the new Council volunteered to subscribe annually to the Indian Exploration Fund in their personal capacity. At last, the Fund was launched on European territory.

Four months later, Führer announced the third great Terai discovery. Piprahwa was a ruined *stupa* on the northern edge of the Birdpore Estate (an indigo plantation managed by William Peppé and his cousin). Following Vincent Smith's advice, the cousins spent their Christmas holiday excavating to the centre of the *stupa*. Within a giant stone chest they found a tiny reliquary deposit. Among the items was the Piprahwa urn that bears a rudimentary Prakrit inscription. In his first communication with European Indologists, Führer spun the text as pre-Ashokan, written near to the time of the Buddha's cremation. The text drew heavily on a reliquary inscription from Amaravati published in 1886.¹⁷

16 Rhys Davids stating that, "I took it for granted that you would not dislike to be President" (ROYAL ASIATIC SOCIETY 1898b).

17 See BURGESS 1886: 106, Inscription 54.

The Indian Exploration Fund was launched at an inauspicious moment, just as perfidious Albion was enmired in the War against the Boers. European opinion favoured the Boers, and was unwilling to donate to a British cause, however worthy. John FLEET suggested that “under existing circumstances” it would best to launch the fund-raising in six months time (ROYAL ASIATIC SOCIETY 1900a). But six months on, Europe was further enraged by the British concentration camps in South Africa. This meeting was notable for being the only time in the Fund’s history when a sensible discussion of target sites took place (ROYAL ASIATIC SOCIETY 1900b).¹⁸ FLEET drafted a preface to a fund-raising document suggesting five specimen sites – Taxila, Savatthi, Ujjain, Banaravasi, and Vijaya Nagara. Meanwhile Lord Reay, having negotiated an understanding with Lord Elgin, had to start again with Lord Curzon. REAY explained what the Fund was intended to achieve,

“One of its objects is to prevent archaeological research from falling into incompetent or unscrupulous hands ... Sir Alfred Lyall is as much alive as I am to the caution that will be required in giving our sanction to foreign explorers” (REAY 1900).

CURZON (1901) was enraged by the “proposal to send a motley crew of international archaeologists rampaging across India”, writing,

“I have not the slightest intention of admitting them to the country ... I do not want a polyglot crew of Germans, French and so on digging about in India, hammering the natives and carrying off our spoil. The project will probably languish for want of funds; and it will certainly meet with no encouragement from me” (*ibid.*).

The Fund could achieve nothing further while Curzon was Viceroy of India. Hence its sponsors waited until Curzon returned to England on leave between April and December 1904.

The decisive Indian Exploration Fund meeting took place in May 1904, and began by counting its assets. The English branch of the Indian Exploration Fund had raised £77, the German branch £35 (collected by local societies in Berlin and Frankfurt), and the Austrian branch “a few guilden” (ROYAL ASIATIC SOCIETY 1904). The joint meeting resolved to offer the sum to Mr. Peppé “either to open a dagoba” (*ibid.*), or to carry out some other prominent work

18 Charles Lyall, Alfred Lyall, John Fleet, Mr. Sewell and Rhys Davids in attendance.

on his estate. Any inscriptions found would belong to the RAS, and everything else to Mr. Peppé. The report on the dig would be published in the *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* (*ibid.*). No inscriptions were found and no report was published, but the 1904 accounts were debited “£130 For Opening Stupa, to Mr. Peppé” (*ibid.*). At that time, £130 equated to Rs.1950 – a substantial amount for an archaeological dig. The meeting was decisive in another sense. John Fleet was so angry at the decision that he declared open war on Rhys Davids, Curzon and Smith and their supporters. Here, I shall have to break with strict chronology, since Fleet’s war was waged as much against the State Patronage funding model as against the foreign donation model.

The State Patronage Model, 1899-1907

Six months after the Piprahwa discovery, Vincent Smith persuaded the Indian Government to put the Piprahwa relics at the centre of Calcutta’s diplomacy. The aim was to recognize the King of Siam as the senior figure in World Buddhism in return for Bangkok’s further subservience to British imperial interests. Once Lord Elgin had agreed, it became an article of British diplomacy that the Piprahwa inscription was a genuine pre-Ashokan text. But then, in September 1898, Führer’s resignation was announced without any further explanation (ANONYMOUS 1898a). An English language paper in Penang added lurid details (ANONYMOUS 1898b). The story was written for the amusement of the expatriate community, but the Thai court, which monitored the Penang press, would have found little amusing in the conjunction of Führer’s admitted forgery of a Buddha-tooth relic with Führer’s close involvement in the discovery and promotion of the Piprahwa bone relics.¹⁹ March 1899 was set for the ceremony at Gorakhpur in which the Piprahwa relics were to be handed over to King Chulalongkorn’s envoy. Lord Elgin, in his final month as Viceroy, apparently was unworried about any threat to the credibility of the relics. In London, the classicists deployed their most senior asset to maintain the credibility of the Terai discoveries by minimizing Führer’s contribution to them. MÜLLER (1898: 788) credited Nigiliva’s discovery to “a Nepalese officer, name unknown” in 1893. He conceded for Paderia

19 Had Bangkok known what Smith, Lord Elgin and Thomas Holderness (Calcutta’s under-secretary in charge of the ASI) knew – that the inscriptions validating both relics had strong similarities – their alarm would have been all the greater.

that Führer's labour in the field was meritorious, but gave most of the credit to Austine Waddell, who had been the first to read *Nigliva* as saying "This is the way to Kapilavastu" (*ibid.*: 791).²⁰ MÜLLER concluded that historians who were sceptical about the finds were being "over-conscientious" and "unreasonable" (*ibid.*). The Nigliva and Paderia Pillars, he assured his audience, "mark the real spots of Buddha's birth and early life" (*ibid.*).

Lord Curzon did perceive a threat to Piprahwa's credibility, and dealt with it energetically and expeditiously. He interviewed the Nepali Prime Minister and ensured his silence. He sent a trusted agent, Surgeon-Doctor Austine Waddell, to inspect the Terai sites. Waddell reported orally in late January, and Curzon decided to let the presentation to Siam proceed. On 1 February 1899, CURZON made his first speech on archaeology,

"I mean to do whatever lies in my power to encourage research, to promote study, and to safeguard the relics of the past as part of our imperial obligation to India" (CURZON 1899).

Thereon, Curzon was committed to a strategy of covering up lingering doubts. It is in this connection that I use the phrase 'State Patronage Model'. Curzon increased the ASI's budget to pay for a Director General and some extra junior posts. I have no objection to state patronage in this form, nor to his funding the ASI to publish *Annual Reports* giving short, accurate accounts of digs undertaken during the previous year. What I object to is funding only one side of an archaeological argument and attempting to silence the other side. Many archaeologists thought Nigliva, Paderia and Piprahwa to be forgeries. Curzon silenced them. Others thought them to be genuine. Curzon sought to have them published with the State's full honours. Dilip CHAKRABARTI (2006: 509) poses an interesting question,

"The new Viceroy showed commitment to archaeology right from the beginning. Whether this was due to his own vision or some other general perception of the period is not determined."

The answer may be that Curzon knew that a Liberal imperialist clique at the RAS had conspired against archaeological truth. He was forced to bribe

20 MÜLLER (1898: 791) added, inaccurately, that Waddell had "with rare pluck searched the pestilential Terai of Nepal" himself. In fact Waddell would not do so until seven weeks after publication.

that clique with increased funding in return for them continuing to support the cover-up.

P.C. Mukherji, who, in January 1899, investigated the Terai discoveries under Vincent Smith's tutelage (while Waddell did so under Curzon's orders), had his report ready for publication by July 1899. Curzon held up its publication, preferring to secure his London allies before publishing native opinion on Nigliva, Paderia, and Piprahwa. He summoned Rhys Davids, editor of the *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, to Calcutta to discuss how to convince the world that the discoveries were genuine. Rhys Davids went straight from the meeting to Peppé's plantation house to relay Curzon's comments to Vincent Smith and Peppé. Rhys Davids then brought William Peppé to London to give a lecture at the RAS. Peppé's lanternslides were admired, and the meeting voted "that Mr. Peppé be requested to carry on his excavations, and that a grant should be made to him for that purpose" (ANONYMOUS 1900a). Rhys Davids briefed the press, and won more favourable stories,

"Back from the birthplace of the Buddha near Basti up from North-east India, Professor Rhys Davids and Mr. Peppé have returned to this country with details of their recent important and interesting discoveries" (ANONYMOUS 1900b).

The *Glasgow Herald* quoted Rhys Davids as being "unequivocal" that this was "the burial place of the great sage" (ANONYMOUS 1900c). There seemed "no reason" to doubt that the Piprahwa inscription is genuine. Piprahwa's identification as the "Stupa of the Sakyas" was clearer cut than for "many of the Holy places of Christian antiquity", and there could be "no doubt" that the script is pre-Ashokan (*ibid.*).

For public consumption, Rhys Davids' meeting with Curzon on the eve of the new century had a different purpose,

"When on an archaeological tour in India in the cold season of 1899-1900, I obtained the honour of an interview with the Viceroy, and was permitted to lay before him the outline of a scheme for the publication of a series of books of reference on the history of India" (RHYS DAVIDS 1907: v).

In a letter to his wife Caroline, RHYS DAVIDS (1900) described the meeting in these terms,

“He did most of the talking nearly, and was evidently determined to do as much as he could, more by far than his predecessors, for archaeology and history. I think our talk, for I had a chance of saying a thing or two, will bear fruit.”

Curzon spent 1901 reorganizing the ASI. That done, in July 1902 he submitted revised plans for an *Indian Texts Series* and an *Indian Record Series*, costing Rs.15,000 a year, to be authorised for a five year period. The *Indian Texts Series* would translate “the works of Indian writers” and “would correspond generally with the Rolls Series, except that it would deal with times prior to British rule” (ROYAL ASIATIC SOCIETY 1902). The *Indian Record Series* would publish English language material from the records of the Indian Government, and “would correspond generally with the English Historical Manuscripts Series” (*ibid.*). A three-way arrangement between patron, publisher, and author requires careful negotiation. The more so, when the patron’s supervisor (the India Office) interposes itself as a fourth party,

“The Council desire to nominate for your approval Professor Rhys Davids as Editor of the *Texts Series* ... In cases of doubt and difficulty Mr. A.N. Wollaston, a Member of the Council of the Royal Asiatic Society, has kindly consented to assist in any way which may appear desirable” (*ibid.*).

Wollaston was indeed an unpaid member of the Council, but his full-time job was Registrar and Superintendent of Records at the India Office. He was one of the many India Office employees who joined the RAS Council between 1898 and 1904. The historian of the RAS says that negotiations were further complicated by,

“... the double role of A.N. Wollaston as representing both the India Office and the Royal Asiatic Society on the negotiations between them ... Attempts were also made to prevent official sponsorship of bad books” (BECKINGHAM 1979: 49).

For which last phrase we may substitute “books which acted as uncritical propaganda for Führer’s Terai discoveries”. P.C. MUKHERJI’s official monograph eventually came out late in 1901. MUKHERJI supported Paderia, but doubted the presence of a *stupa* at Nigiliva (see MUKHERJI 1901). Yet a Parisian scholar had discredited his work for digging “rather uselessly” at Pataliputta, and for his remarks on Kusinagara,

“On the very lightest evidence, without the slightest hesitation, he placed it at Lauriya Nandangarh, with its inscribed Ashokan lion pillar ... His *Preliminary Report*, dateline Bankipur 30 April 1897, reads like a bad novel and, in truth, does not bode well for Kapilavatthu” (BARTH 1900: 179).

As for the whole theory that the Buddha was born in Nepal,

“It is not just that the bearings no longer carry conviction, but that trust has been shaken. Naturally also the methodology itself has been put in question” (*ibid.*).

No European would commit to writing a second monograph, which left the possibility of endorsing the finds via either a work on Buddhist geography, or a work on Brahmi epigraphy.²¹ A work on historical maps could locate Lumbini at Paderia, and Kapilavatthu a few miles west of Nigliva. An epigraphic collection could bring the Paderia, Nigliva and Piprahwa inscriptions within the canon by printing them alongside the genuine Brahmi inscriptions found at Mathura and Bharhut. The RAS Council was convulsed by two crises: the first, from June 1904 to February 1905, concerned a proposed *Texts Series* work on historical geography; the second, from March to November 1906, concerned a proposed *Texts Series* collection of Brahmi epigraphy.

John Fleet, as we have seen, was enraged by the decision in May 1904 to give the Indian Exploration Fund money to William Peppé for a dig somewhere on his indigo estate at Birdpore. A week later, Fleet discovered that Rhys Davids had taken unauthorized and surreptitious action in relation to the *Texts Series*. First, Rhys Davids had allocated volumes to editors – for instance, a volume of *Historical Maps of India* – without consulting the RAS Council. Secondly, that Rhys Davids was being paid secretly to edit a volume for the *Texts Series*. Thirdly, that Rhys Davids was in secret discussion with a commercial publisher, Messrs John Murray, to sub-delegate production of the *Texts Series* and *Historical Series* from the RAS. Fleet pinned up two incendiary motions for debate at the 14 June Council meeting. These motions called into question Rhys Davids’ honour and integrity. Whichever way the Council voted, either the accuser or the accused would have to resign from the RAS. Eighteen members of the Council attended the Wednesday evening

21 Brāhmī being the script in which all three Terai inscriptions are written.

Council meeting, over which Lord Reay presided. Broadly speaking, Fleet won the day's battle, though Rhys Davids was allowed to present his full defence at the Council's next monthly meeting. In July, Rhys Davids admitted all three of Fleet's charges, but argued that they were all sensible decisions that the Council should retrospectively endorse. When that secret correspondence between Rhys Davids, the India Office and Calcutta was published, it showed that Rhys Davids planned a volume of *Historical Maps of India* to be published in 1904, with contributions by himself and Vincent Smith, and a volume of Kharosthi inscriptions to be edited by Mr. Rapson and M. Bergny. Through the winter of 1904, Rhys Davids tried to muster support in the various sub-committees that investigated aspects of the case against him. On Saint Valentine's Day 1905, Rhys Davids tendered his resignation as RAS Secretary and as the editor of the *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* (ROYAL ASIATIC SOCIETY 1905).

Lord Curzon had returned to Calcutta to regain his Viceroyship while Rhys Davids' future was yet undecided. Evidently he had already washed his hands of the Rhys Davids ploy. In 1905, the *Records Series* was withdrawn from the RAS, and the *Texts Series* was also withdrawn after one volume had appeared (BECKINGHAM 1979: 49).

Instead, Curzon began to work through the young India Office Librarian, F.W. Thomas. Thomas was a working-class lad propelled into high Imperial politics by his success in the Cambridge Oriental tripos. While the Fleet-Rhys Davids battle still raged, Thomas suggested to Curzon in August that the Kharosthi inscriptions volumes be removed from *Indian Texts* to *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*. One of Curzon-in-Council's first acts on returning to India was to endorse this suggestion, and to take a bold step closer to an official endorsement of the Terai inscriptions,

“We would however suggest that the work now under consideration, which should deal with Kharosthi and Brahmi-Kharosthi inscriptions, should be treated as Part 1 of the volume, and that a second part dealing with Brahmi inscriptions should be separately issued” (CURZON 1904).²²

22 My thanks to Antonia Moon, Keeper of the India Office Records, for allowing the file to have a reference number.

THOMAS (1905) minuted to Wollaston that the suggestion of a Brahmi volume was “eminently reasonable and calls for the grateful recognition of students”. He added that nothing should be said to the RAS as yet, since “presumably the invitation to the R. Asiatic Society is for the moment in abeyance” (*ibid.*). Though they kept the RAS in the dark, they apparently discussed the new development with Rhys Davids, who suggested R.O. Franke of Königsberg to edit the Brahmi volume. For a whole year nothing further was done. Then, in late April 1906, Thomas wrote to the RAS mentioning for the first time the prospect of a volume on Brahmi inscriptions. Miss Hughes read the letter in consternation. The next Council meeting appointed a new sub-committee, comprising George Grierson, John Fleet and Moses Gaster, to report on the proposal. Meanwhile HUGHES replied to Wollaston that the “‘Brahmi-Kharosthi’ expression” was altogether inapt for the epigraphy volume so far under discussion, and asked him to “Tell me what is really intended – the committee is soon sitting” (HUGHES 1906).

Fleet’s Sub-Committee sat on 23 March, and reported that they were,

“... not prepared at the present moment to name anyone, British or otherwise, to whom the editing of the Brahmi inscriptions might advantageously now be definitely entrusted. For a full statement of their reasons, and of certain recommendations which they make, the Committee invite perusal of the annexed memorandum, drawn up by Mr. Fleet and adopted by the Committee” (ROYAL ASIATIC SOCIETY 1906).

FLEET’s *Memorandum*, now available to the public after 110 years, reveals the heart of the Fleet-Davids dispute. FLEET (n.d.: 4) makes a simple point, then repeats it,

“Many of the published reproductions are notoriously untrustworthy as having been produced from copies made by hand, or from impressions, estampages, photographs, and proofs, which have been touched up by hand.”

On page 5, he writes, “Some members of the archaeological establishments in India have still to realize that those materials ... must be prepared by purely mechanical means, without any touching up by hand” (*ibid.*: 5). On page 7, he mentions “reliable ink impressions and estampages, prepared by purely mechanical means and according to the excellent processes now available” (*ibid.*: 7). In relation to Piprahwa, it is clear which are the “notoriously

untrustworthy” published illustrations that he objects to. August BARTH published Führer’s touched-up “rubbing” in 1898 (see BARTH 1898). PEPPÉ, with Vincent Smith’s help, published his two-line transcription of the single line inscription two months later (PEPPÉ 1898: 577). In the same issue, RHYS DAVIDS (1898: 579) published two unhelpfully small views of it, overtowered by large photographs of the (genuine) Sonari inscription. He reproduced the same plate in his *Buddhist India* (RHYS DAVIDS 1903: 577). Vincent SMITH’s photograph of the urn inscription (which looks as if lip-stick has been used to highlight the syllables) also appeared in his *Early History of India* (1904).

Fleet intended his *Memorandum* as a veiled threat to the pro-cover-up clique in the India Office: “If you continue with your present plans”, he was saying, “I shall publicly expose all three Terai forgeries”. Lord Reay might have approved the exposure, had it just been a matter of exposing some recent Tory scandals. But the Terai forgeries originated with the Liberal imperialist administration of 1894-95, who had kept Führer in his job, publicized the Nigliva finds on Führer’s terms, and rewarded Rhys Davids with a civil pension. Lord Reay quickly gave Fleet assurances that if a Brahmi volume ever were compiled, it would not be a Curzon-style endorsement of Piprahwa and Paderia. On 19 June, a ceremony was held at the RAS to award Dr. Pope a medal for his work on Tamil languages. Fortuitously, Secretary of State Morley was present at Albemarle Street to make the presentation. In moving the vote of thanks to Mr. Morley, Lord REAY (1906: 785-788) touched on controversial matters,

“There is still a good deal of spade-work to be done, as is evident from the memorandum of Dr. Fleet on the second volume of the *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*, which will deal with the so-called Kharosthi and Brahmi inscriptions. Dr. Fleet has shown in the third volume of the *Corpus* dealing with the Gupta inscriptions how the difficulties peculiar to the work can be overcome.”

In other words, Lord Reay, with Mr. Morley’s silent endorsement, promised that any Brahmi volume would be edited to Fleet’s exacting standards.

After a two-month delay, F.W. Thomas publicly endorsed all six of Fleet’s recommendations. But in private he wrote a lengthy handwritten minute criticizing every aspect of Fleet’s *Memorandum*. It is a “highly controversial document”, which has been “severely criticised by the Librarian”,

“Mr. Fleet’s memorandum being of the nature described, it would appear to be undesirable to send it without the Librarian’s comments. Mr Thomas agrees with the Department that it is better that neither document be sent” (THOMAS 1906).

FLEET’s *Memorandum* was never published, contrary to the RAS’ wishes. *Au contraire*, the Keeper of Indian Office Records used his skills as an archivist to make the file disappear for 105 years. The only clue as to the technique he deployed is the phrase “Special Box” written at the top of its headsheet.

Let us return to the India Exploration Fund’s dig on the Birdpore Estate, authorized in May 1904. Someone (perhaps Fleet) asked John Marshall and his ASI to keep an eye on events. In February 1905, J.Ph. Vogel (who took over Führer’s old job in 1903) visited Dulha (Basti district) to examine “a building excavated by Mr Duncan Rickets, Manager of the Dulha Estate, at the request of the Royal Asiatic Society” (VOGEL 1905: 2). He stated that the excavation “proved to have yielded little of value” (*ibid.*). Vogel took a couple of photographs of the site, a detail from one of which is reproduced below (**Fig. 1**). Vogel and Mr. and Mrs. Rickets appear to be sitting in a half-

Fig. 1 Photograph of Jean Vogel, and Mr. and Mrs. Rickets at the excavations at Dulha, 1905 (after VOGEL 1905)

excavated monastery. The Dulha Estate lay to the east of Peppé's Birdpore Estate, and was nearly as large. Its north end was close to Paderia, while its southern end was said to contain several Buddhist ruins. It would be interesting to learn where on the estate the photograph was taken. There was an oblique mention in the 1908 accounts to £50 being credited to the Exploration Expenses Account, marked "refund of amount unexpended", then again, in the 1914 accounts, £65 is credited to the Fund as "refund of balance by Mr Peppé".²³ All but £15 of the £130 handed over to Peppé in 1904 was eventually repaid to the Fund.

Doubtless these enigmatic events are explained in *Mr. Peppé's report on the expenditure of the money entrusted to him for exploration*, submitted in 1914. Unfortunately the ephemera of the RAS remain uncatalogued. If the report still exists, it has not yet been located.

Conclusions

Until Lord Elgin became Viceroy, informed participants held reasoned debate over how to fund Indological research. After 1894, the debate turned conspiratorial. The Indian Exploration Fund conspired against Lord Curzon. Lord Curzon conspired against the Council of the Royal Asiatic Society. General issues about funding became tangled with specific issues about Führer's discoveries at Nigliva and Paderia, and the Peppé-Smith discovery at Piprahwa. The Indian Exploration Fund and the Terai discoveries were discussed together (see BARTH 1900: 179). In John Fleet's mind, the *Indian Texts Series* and the Piprahwa inscription merged into a single issue (FLEET n.d.).²⁴ Some reputations – notably those of Alois Führer, Vincent Smith, and Rhys Davids – need radical revision.

Yet let us ever strive to look on the bright side. The RAS Council proved capable of purging one, at least, of the wrong-doers, and of preventing any more archaeological lies being disseminated in its name. True, it was not strong enough to publish full details of the conspiracy against the Buddhist Holy Land. It could not admit that the Piprahwa inscription was an 1890s forgery, but it could argue that it was written well after Ashoka, and had little to do with the events described in the *Sutta of the Great Decease*. This

²³ Records of the accounts of the RAS, held in the archives of the Royal Asiatic Society.

²⁴ Cf. FLEET 1905a, 1905b, 1906a, 1906b.

process began as early as 1901. Lt.-Gov. MACDONNELL (1901), who had been on leave throughout the Piprahwa diplomacy, listed the North-Western Provinces and Oudh's archaeological achievements "during the last six years". He mentions none of the Terai discoveries by name, saying only that,

"During Dr. Führer's incumbency a report began by him, completed by Mr. P.C. Mukherji, and edited by Mr. Vincent Smith, I.C.S., on excavations at the supposed site of Kapilavastu was submitted by this Government to the Government of India. It has not yet been published" (*ibid.*).

His private opinion was that Alois Führer's archaeological statements should "only be accepted if independently verified" (MACDONNELL 1899), and that Vincent Smith was inexpert both in monumental archaeology and epigraphy: "As Director-General of Archaeology I fear he would be found wanting" (MACDONNELL n.d.). By the 1910s, the Paderia site, "the birthplace of the Buddha", was deserted and partly overgrown, and the Terai discoveries were no longer mentioned in polite archaeological discussion.

This happy compromise was the work of John Faithfull Fleet (1847-1917) who surely deserves to be celebrated as the RAS's most valiant warrior on behalf of truth. His epigraphic articles suggest a dry, over-cautious personality, but the way he conducted his successful campaign against Rhys Davids, Curzon, and the India Office suggests a seasoned bureaucratic in-fighter of the highest calibre. And how refreshing that Fleet used his skills in service of academic truth, rather than in furthering his own career or in promoting his own policies to govern India!

*Laudamus, igitur, Ioannem Fidelem Celerem
In veritate fidelis, in corrigendo celer.*

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